

PHILOSOPHY

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STRUCTURAL SYMBOLIC ELEMENTS IN VIRTUAL COMMUNICATION

In modern society, there is a densification and integration of communication structures driven by the advancement of internet technologies, encompassing diverse forms of interaction increasingly accessible due to the network's technical capabilities. Since the late 20th and early 21st centuries, there has been a significant growth in virtual social networks, serving as a crucial platform for online communication, gathering billions of users of various social affiliations, thereby creating a unique «existence» in the online space defined by interaction and communication.

Virtual dialogue possesses unique characteristics and ontological features distinguishing it from face-to-face communication. Virtual space provides anonymity, influencing the behavior and speech of dialogue participants and giving rise to multiple identities. The absence of immediate physical contact and delayed reactions can affect the nature and content of the dialogue, granting participants greater control over their expressions and perceptions by others. Research on symbols conducted by philosophers such as C.G. Jung, E. Cassirer, M. Heidegger, J. Lacan, M. Foucault, contributes significantly to our understanding of human experience and social reality. They view symbols as a key element in understanding and organizing our world, as well as a means of creating meaning and understanding life. The structure of the symbolic aspect of virtual reality differs from that of physical reality, yet both are manifestations of deeper structures.

These structures, present in both factual reality and its symbolic representation, reflect the integral properties of human consciousness and culture, serving as a bridge between the external and internal worlds of the individual, allowing translation between these two levels of reality. This underscores the importance of the symbolic in our interaction with the world, confirming that without it, our experience and understanding of reality would be limited [1].

Virtual reality also opens up opportunities for multi-channel communication and blurring the boundaries between personal and public existence, potentially fostering the emergence of new forms of communication and relationships. Additionally, symbolic elements such as internet memes, emoji's, hashtags, and others play a pivotal role in information exchange and user communication in the digital environment, offering participant's new means of expression and interaction. Structurally symbolic elements in virtual communication resemble myth in Roland Barthes' interpretation. Virtual communication has the ability to shape and redefine social reality through symbolic exchanges, creating a unique «virtual reality» through communication and interaction. Symbols and signs in virtual reality play a crucial role in expressing personality and forming virtual identity, representing a system of signs, codes, and symbols used for transmitting and interpreting information in the digital realm. This socio-ontological phenomenon has its own characteristics and foundations that define the meaning and significance of symbols in the context of virtual communication [2].

The symbolic form in virtual communication creates its own ontology based on the use of symbols and signs in the communication process, contributing to the formation and maintenance of connections between participants in virtual communication, reflecting the combination of social and ontological foundations of virtual communication. The social and ontological foundations of the symbolic form in virtual communication reflect the interrelationship between social structures and the symbolic system of virtual space.

These constructs become reality through interaction between subjects and serve as the basis for forming an autonomous subsystem of virtual reality within the broader multidimensional real world. Symbols not only represent or depict reality but also actively participate in its formation and interpretation [3]. People use symbols to create meaning, structure their experiences, and organize their world. It is important to note that symbolic elements are constantly supplemented, evolve, and adapt in response to changes in culture and technology. Symbols can be reinterpreted, redesigned, and reinterpreted depending on social and cultural changes. They can have various layers of meaning that may intersect, contradict each other, or change depending on the context.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that modern internet technologies contribute to the densification and integration of communication structures, expanding the

accessibility of various forms of communication and interaction. The growth of virtual social networks creates a unique online space where virtual dialogue, with its distinct characteristics, differs from face-to-face communication. Research on symbols conducted by philosophers not only contributes significantly to our understanding of human experience and social reality but also underscores the importance of symbolic interaction in the context of virtual space, where symbolic elements play a crucial role. Symbols and signs play a key role in expressing personality and shaping virtual identity, forming a system of signs and codes for transmitting and interpreting information. The interconnection between social structures and the symbolic system of virtual space shapes an autonomous subsystem of virtual reality within a broader multidimensional world. The symbolic form in virtual communication constitutes a foundational system that fosters connections between communication participants and reflects socio-cultural changes, highlighting their dynamic nature and adaptability.

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